

Application form: Open Science Infrastructure (2024) - Pre-proposal

Section 1 – Applicant(s)

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Section 2 - Summary

Proposed project title	ReproHub: Enhanced Replicability and Open Science Education for Research with Secondary and Sensitive Data
Project type	Large
Project duration (in months)	48 months

Section 3 – Project description

3.1 Alignment of your project with the aim of the call

Vision and Targeted Open Science Challenges

The adoption of open science practices among social scientists has doubled over the past decade as the scientific community increasingly prioritizes **transparency and reproducibility** (Ferguson et al., 2023). However, across the different domains of science, the **implementation of open science principles remains uneven**. ODISSEI, the Dutch national infrastructure for social sciences, observes this dilemma firsthand, especially within **secondary data-intensive research**, where data protection and ownership issues complicate open science practices. Despite the availability of platforms (e.g., Dataverse) and tools (e.g., Git for version control and Make for build automation), many researchers share only minimally documented, computationally irreproducible data packages. We believe this issue stems from two main challenges: first, secondary data researchers that conduct research with sensitive data **often lack easy-to-access tools**, and second, even tech-savvy researchers find **existing solutions impractical and inaccessible**, as these tend to prioritize technical sophistication over user-friendliness and accessibility (Van Lissa et al., 2021; Peikert et al., 2021).

These gaps highlight the urgent need to improve infrastructure that **helps Dutch researchers who rely on sensitive secondary data** to follow open science principles. This project combines the efforts of two successful existing open science infrastructure solutions: Tilburg Science Hub (TSH) and ODISSEI. Launched at Tilburg University in 2019, TSH offers accessible open science tools, a **user-friendly platform**, and precise documentation that builds researchers' open science skills. It has earned a reputation as a **trusted resource for researchers and students seeking advice on adopting** open science practices. TSH now attracts over 450,000 visitors annually from institutions worldwide. Through the committed integration of TSH with ODISSEI's existing services—such as SoDA (Social Data Analytics), the ODISSEI Summer School on Computational Social Science, the ODISSEI Code Library, and the ODISSEI Portal—this project will **strengthen Dutch infrastructure supporting open science across disciplines**.

The goal of this project is to build on this success and, with the support of ODISSEI, **scale TSH to the national level** while **simultaneously expanding its functionality** to cater to the needs of secondary data-intensive research. Our work would include solutions for certifying research reproducibility, improving research discoverability, and applying AI to automate reproducibility workflows. Specifically, key objectives include automating quality checks on replication packages (i.e., archives containing the code and data needed to replicate study findings), enabling **secure execution of privacy-sensitive data analyses** (e.g., within ODISSEI's Secure Analysis Environment, SANE), **training students and faculty**, and **raising the visibility of open science practices**. By combining the open science expertise of both ODISSEI and TSH with the methodological insights of a diverse team of researchers from Tilburg University and Erasmus University, this project meets the **growing demand of Dutch academics for open science support** by helping to create an inclusive, transparent, and reproducible research ecosystem.

Alignment with Open Science Principles

The proposed project is conceptually and technically well-aligned with open science principles. The current and future planned infrastructure embodies core open science principles by combining **technical openness with robust privacy protection**. Built on open-source technologies—Python and Flask for core functionality, containerized deployment, and Git for version control—all components are publicly available on GitHub with comprehensive documentation and contribution workflows in machine-readable markdown. The platform, in general, and the functionalities to be developed, in particular, enable research that is 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary' by separating analytical workflows from privacy-sensitive data through the use of **differentially private techniques** (Dwork and Roth, 2014), and **standardized data-handling documentation**.

This approach is aligned with the guiding principles of the NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda, the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2018), and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2023). The infrastructure adheres to community standards, including FAIR principles, standardized replication formats, and data dictionaries, while ensuring data remains secure in approved environments. This approach extends open science capabilities to fields traditionally constrained by data sensitivity, such as healthcare and finance, while maintaining the highest standards of research transparency. Thus, the project plays a key role in achieving the goals put forward in the NPOS 2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda, making open science the norm for output produced by knowledge institutions in the Netherlands.

3.2 Project plan

The project involves **developing new functionalities and creating and sharing educational material, including guidance on their use**. Our approach combines agile methods with continuous user feedback and integration to meet researchers' needs effectively. The work packages will be executed in parallel. WP1, WP2, and WP4 address feature development, while WP3 focuses on generating and disseminating related educational content.

Work Package 1 (ReproBuddy) develops an AI-powered assistant for automating replication package improvements. Using an open-source LLM with retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) for fine-tuning, ReproBuddy provides contextual guidance on code automation, documentation, version control, and data dictionaries. It learns from user interactions to improve recommendations for common reproducibility challenges.

Work Package 2 (ReproRun) creates a secure computational environment using Docker containerization and differential privacy techniques to enable reproducibility certification while protecting sensitive data. It includes automated verification tools and templates for documenting computational workflows integrating with SANE.

Work Package 3 (Tilburg Science Hub) expands TSH's educational platform to support capacity-building with structured educational content, hands-on workshops, and direct integration with research support services at Tilburg University, Erasmus University Rotterdam, and ODISSEI's network.

Work Package 4 (OpenScienceRadar) develops a browser extension to enhance open science visibility, combining automated journal policy detection with crowd-sourced data collection.

Standardized APIs and shared infrastructure will enable integration across packages. ODISSEI's researcher network, Open Science Communities in Tilburg and Rotterdam (OSCO), and TSH will regularly conduct user testing to ensure solutions remain accessible, effective, and responsive to evolving research needs.

3.3 Team composition

Name and position	Expertise	Contribution to WP			
		1	2	3	4
Hannes Datta (Assoc. Prof., TiSEM/TiU)	Platform development, AI integration	x	x	x	x
Tom Emery (Assoc. Prof. Erasmus U; Deputy Director of ODISSEI)	Social science data, alignment with ODISSEI and its member organizations	x	x	x	x
Ana Martinovici (Assis. Prof., RSM/Erasmus, STAR editor at Psych. Science)	Teaching and implementing OS practices, replication package checks at journals	x	x	x	
Lachlan Deer (Assis. Prof., TiSEM/TiU)	Reproducible workflows with secondary data	x			
Tobias Klein (Prof., TiSEM/TiU)	Econometrics, reproducible research				x
Matthijs van Gils (Project manager at Tilburg.ai, junior lecturer at TiU)	Project management, AI integration, RAG, deployment and IT infrastructure	x	x	x	x
Shrabastee Banerjee (Assis. Prof., TiU)	Digital platforms, OS dissemination			x	
Alexander Vossen (Assis. Prof., JADS)	Workflows for proprietary data, data science		x		
Caspar van Lissa (Assoc. Prof., TSB/TiU; Chair of the OS Community Tilburg)	Open reproducible code in science, machine learning (ML)		x		
Julian R.K. Wichmann (Assis. Prof., TiSEM/TiU)	Digital platforms, developer of popular browser extension				x
Stefan Kirsch (RSE, TSB/TiU)	Researcher engagement and research tooling		x		x
Aurélie Lemmens (Prof., RSM/Erasmus U)	Responsible data science, causal ML			x	
Gilian Ponte (Assis. Prof. RSM/Erasmus U)	Differential privacy, data sharing		x		

References

- Dwork, C., & Roth, A. (2014). The algorithmic foundations of differential privacy. *Foundations and Trends® in Theoretical Computer Science*, 9(3–4), 211–407. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1561/04000000042>
- Ferguson, J., Littman, R., ... & Pezzuto, J.-H. (2023). Survey of open science practices and attitudes in the social sciences. *Nature Communications*, 14(1), 5401. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41111-1>
- Peikert, A., Van Lissa, C. J., & Brandmaier, A. M. (2021). Reproducible research in R: A tutorial on how to do the same thing more than once. *Psych*, 3(4), 836–867. <https://doi.org/10.3390/psych3040053>
- Van Lissa, C. J., Brandmaier, A. M. et al. (2021). WORCS: A workflow for open, reproducible code in science. *Data Science*, 4(1), 29–49. <https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-210031>

Section 4 – Budget

Type of costs	Short explanation	Costs
Personnel costs	<p>The project comprises 4 work packages (WPs), each supported by a collaborative team of senior researchers (0.1–0.2 FTE per researcher) working alongside junior researchers (see Section 3.3; also for 0.1-0.2 FTE) and 2-4 student research assistants (0.2–0.4 FTE) per work package, under the guidance of senior team members. Each work package will also benefit from the specialized technical expertise of an engineering doctorate student (EngD) (placed at JADS in 's-Hertogenbosch), who will provide technical development and design support across tasks at a commitment of 1 FTE for two years (years 2-3).</p> <p>ODISSEI will provide in-kind support by covering its own personnel costs, enabling researchers in WPs 1-4 to collaborate seamlessly with ODISSEI staff within their existing roles.</p> <p>A full-time project manager will oversee coordination, alignment across work packages, nationwide academic engagement, and milestone tracking.</p>	€ 1,425,000
Other costs	<p>Key additional costs include hosting fees for the platform, an external designer for adapting TSH's user-friendly interface to incorporate the planned new functionality, and travel expenses for conferences and stakeholder meetings. Communication and outreach efforts, including social media and newsletters, will engage the academic and practitioner communities effectively.</p>	€ 75,000
Total request from NWO		€ 1,500,000

Section 5 – Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organization has been informed of this grant application, and the research organization accepts the grant conditions of this program.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.